

Supplementary Online Content

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Supplement Table S1 Associations of olive oil and other vegetable oil consumption with heart disease and stroke mortality

	Vegetable oil consumption	
	No	Yes
Olive oil		
Heart disease mortality		
Deaths/person-years	118/19592	62/19473
Model 1	1.00 (Ref.)	0.44 (0.27-0.72)
Model 2	1.00 (Ref.)	0.56 (0.32-0.97)
Model 3	1.00 (Ref.)	0.55 (0.32-0.97)
Stroke mortality		
Deaths/person-years	25/19592	15/19473
Model 1	1.00 (Ref.)	0.75 (0.30-1.88)
Model 2	1.00 (Ref.)	0.83 (0.31-2.21)
Model 3	1.00 (Ref.)	0.81 (0.31-2.09)
Corn oil		
Heart disease mortality		
Deaths/person-years	115/26333	65/12732
Model 1	1.00 (Ref.)	1.56 (0.96-2.52)
Model 2	1.00 (Ref.)	1.31 (0.79-2.17)
Model 3	1.00 (Ref.)	1.33 (0.81-2.17)
Stroke mortality		
Deaths/person-years	27/26333	13/12732
Model 1	1.00 (Ref.)	0.95 (0.41-2.20)
Model 2	1.00 (Ref.)	0.94 (0.36-2.45)
Model 3	1.00 (Ref.)	0.95 (0.37-2.40)
Canola/rapeseed oil		
Heart disease mortality		
Deaths/person-years	124/24388	56/14677
Model 1	1.00 (Ref.)	0.81 (0.47-1.40)
Model 2	1.00 (Ref.)	1.00 (0.58-1.75)
Model 3	1.00 (Ref.)	1.00 (0.56-1.80)
Stroke mortality		
Deaths/person-years	31/24388	9/14677
Model 1	1.00 (Ref.)	1.17 (0.49-2.80)
Model 2	1.00 (Ref.)	1.16 (0.49-2.79)
Model 3	1.00 (Ref.)	1.12 (0.47-2.65)

Model 1: Adjusted for age, sex, and race/ethnicity.

Model 2: Adjusted for covariates in model 1 plus education, family income, smoking status, alcohol intake, physical activity, HEI-2015, and total energy intake.

Model 3: Adjusted for covariates in model 2 plus body mass index (calculated as kg/m^2).

Supplement Table S2 Associations of vegetable oil consumption with heart disease and stroke mortality

	Vegetable oil consumption			
	No vegetable oil	Olive oil exclusively	Olive oil and other vegetable oil	Other vegetable oil
Heart disease mortality				
Deaths/person-years	39/4276	18/7401	40/11427	83/15963
Model 1	1.00 (Ref.)	0.27 (0.15-0.48)	0.43 (0.21-0.87)	0.76 (0.52-1.11)
Model 2	1.00 (Ref.)	0.33 (0.16-0.69)	0.56 (0.24-1.31)	0.76 (0.49-1.18)
Model 3	1.00 (Ref.)	0.34 (0.17-0.70)	0.58 (0.25-1.35)	0.78 (0.50-1.22)
Stroke mortality				
Deaths/person-years	7/4276	7/7401	8/11427	18/15963
Model 1	1.00 (Ref.)	0.44 (0.10-1.92)	0.60 (0.15-2.43)	0.56 (0.15-2.08)
Model 2	1.00 (Ref.)	0.56 (0.14-2.31)	0.75 (0.16-3.44)	0.66 (0.18-2.41)
Model 3	1.00 (Ref.)	0.54 (0.13-2.23)	0.70 (0.16-2.96)	0.65 (0.19-2.19)

Model 1: Adjusted for age, sex, and race/ethnicity.

Model 2: Adjusted for covariates in model 1 plus education, family income, smoking status, alcohol intake, physical activity, HEI-2015, and total energy intake.

Model 3: Adjusted for covariates in model 2 plus body mass index (calculated as kg/m²).

Supplement Table S3 Associations of exclusive olive oil consumption frequency with heart disease and stroke mortality

	No vegetable oil	Frequency of exclusive olive oil consumption	
		<1 time/mo to ≤1 time/wk	≥2 times/wk
Heart disease mortality			
Deaths/person-years	39/4276	9/3762	9/3639
Model 1	1.00 (Ref.)	0.31 (0.13-0.74)	0.26 (0.12-0.59)
Model 2	1.00 (Ref.)	0.30 (0.09-0.94)	0.21 (0.08-0.57)
Model 3	1.00 (Ref.)	0.32 (0.10-1.08)	0.22 (0.08-0.60)
Stroke mortality			
Deaths/person-years	7/4276	5/3762	2/3639
Model 1	1.00 (Ref.)	0.65 (0.10-4.27)	0.31 (0.04-2.22)
Model 2	1.00 (Ref.)	0.81 (0.26-2.57)	0.29 (0.03-2.55)
Model 3	1.00 (Ref.)	0.85 (0.25-2.82)	0.26 (0.04-1.65)

Model 1: Adjusted for age, sex, and race/ethnicity.

Model 2: Adjusted for covariates in model 1 plus education, family income, smoking status, alcohol intake, physical activity, HEI-2015, and total energy intake.

Model 3: Adjusted for covariates in model 2 plus body mass index (calculated as kg/m²).

Supplement Table S4 Associations of exclusive corn oil consumption frequency with heart disease and stroke mortality

	No vegetable oil	Frequency of exclusive corn oil consumption	
		<1 time/mo to ≤1 time/wk	≥2 times/wk
Heart disease mortality			
Deaths/person-years	39/4276	14/2535	17/2856
Model 1	1.00 (Ref.)	0.96 (0.46-2.02)	0.66 (0.37-1.18)
Model 2	1.00 (Ref.)	0.57 (0.28-1.15)	0.50 (0.23-1.09)
Model 3	1.00 (Ref.)	0.58 (0.28-1.21)	0.51 (0.23-1.13)
Stroke mortality			
Deaths/person-years	7/4276	3/2535	5/2856
Model 1	1.00 (Ref.)	0.27 (0.05-1.53)	0.35 (0.09-1.36)
Model 2	1.00 (Ref.)	0.36 (0.06-2.25)	0.41 (0.12-1.35)
Model 3	1.00 (Ref.)	0.20 (0.01-2.96)	0.36 (0.10-1.33)

Model 1: Adjusted for age, sex, and race/ethnicity.

Model 2: Adjusted for covariates in model 1 plus education, family income, smoking status, alcohol intake, physical activity, HEI-2015, and total energy intake.

Model 3: Adjusted for covariates in model 2 plus body mass index (calculated as kg/m²).

Supplement Table 5 Associations of exclusive canola oil consumption frequency with heart disease and stroke mortality

	No vegetable oil	Frequency of exclusive canola oil consumption	
		<1 time/mo to ≤1 time/wk	≥2 times/wk
Heart disease mortality			
Deaths/person-years	39/4276	10/2477	13/2453
Model 1	1.00 (Ref.)	0.37 (0.16-0.87)	0.83 (0.36-1.91)
Model 2	1.00 (Ref.)	0.31 (0.12-0.78)	0.60 (0.21-1.68)
Model 3	1.00 (Ref.)	0.30 (0.12-0.78)	0.62 (0.22-1.73)
Stroke mortality			
Deaths/person-years	7/4276	2/2477	2/2453
Model 1	1.00 (Ref.)	1.28 (0.29-5.75)	0.21 (0.02-1.77)
Model 2	1.00 (Ref.)	1.43 (0.34-6.00)	0.75 (0.08-6.60)
Model 3	1.00 (Ref.)	1.20 (0.37-3.84)	0.80 (0.08-7.84)

Model 1: Adjusted for age, sex, and race/ethnicity.

Model 2: Adjusted for covariates in model 1 plus education, family income, smoking status, alcohol intake, physical activity, HEI-2015, and total energy intake.

Model 3: Adjusted for covariates in model 2 plus body mass index (calculated as kg/m²).